

Interview Setup and Script -

1) Introduction-

*“Good Morning! (any appropriate greetings depending on the time of day)
Thank you for participating in our interview study. I am [Interviewer Name], doing my research at [University Name]. Today, we will discuss your experiences related to Unified Payments Interface (UPI) transactions in India.”*

2) Overview-

“During this interview, we are interested in gaining a deeper understanding of your experiences, challenges, and awareness regarding UPI usage. We value your input and assure you that there are no right or wrong answers. We're not here to test your knowledge but to gather your thoughts and views about UPI.”

3) Consent-

“Before we proceed, I would like to remind you that when we reached out to you via call/text/email to confirm your participation, you provided your consent. It's essential to reiterate that what you share with us during this interview will be treated with the utmost confidentiality. If at any point you feel uncomfortable or prefer not to answer a particular question, please let us know. You have the right to stop participating at any time, and there will be no consequences for doing so. ”

4) Questions before beginning-

“Before we start recording and continue the interview, do you have any questions about the procedure or anything you'd like to know?”

5) Recording-

- The call recording part will be from the beginning of the questionnaire (we will inform the participant about it).
- The interviewer will verify that the call recording is enabled for the mobile/interview application being used.

Start recording:

This is [Interviewer Name] leading interview number # and just to have it on record, you consent to being recorded, right?

Research Questions -

1. What are UPI user security perceptions, concerns, behaviors, and rationales?
2. Where do they learn their security awareness and behavior?

3. How does this correspond to official advice from banks, UPI providers, and regulatory bodies?

Interview Questions

Section 1 - Participant's UPI Background

- 1) Can you tell us a bit about your background, about your education, work, etc.?
[Note - In the consent form, demographics will be collected and include educational background details]
- 2) When and how did you first get to know about UPI?
- 3) Have you got any help to signup to UPI app?
- 4) How long have you been using UPI? And why did you start using it?
- 5) How often do you use it?

Section 2 - UPI Usage Questions

- 6) What are the major reasons for using UPI? When do you use it most?
[Probe - Business, Personal transactions]
- 7) What are the most common types of transactions you make using UPI?
[Probe - Any recurring payments set for bills (Gas, DTH, water etc), booking flight tickets, trains, online shopping, food ordering, transactions with family and friends etc.]
- 8) Which UPI applications do you use? Is there any reason to use this application?
[Probe - Stand-alone UPI apps or bank UPI apps]
- 9) Which devices do you commonly use for UPI transactions?
[Probe- Have you used anything other than your mobile phone?]
- 10) If you use UPI regularly, walk us through your typical day and all the transactions you make using UPI.
[Probe - Paying taxi fare for daily commute, food courts, etc.]
- 11) How do you usually check if the UPI transactions are successful or not?
[Probe - Both ways like receiving and sending money]

Section 3 - Information Sources and Learning

- 12) Do you recall your first experience with UPI? How did you learn to use it?

[Probe - Did you receive or look for information on how to use UPI when you started using it?]

- If yes, from where did you get that information?

13) What are some practices you follow to stay safe while doing UPI transactions? Where did you get this information from?

[Example - Family/friends/colleagues, internet, advertisements]

14) Have you experienced any scams or frauds while using UPI, could you share your experiences?

- If not, Have you heard of any scams or frauds on UPI from others?
- How did these experiences and stories impact you? Did you take any action to stay safe after hearing these stories? What extra care did you start taking after that?

15) What information do you wish you knew before using UPI?

Section 4 - Concerns and Challenges

16) Are there any challenges you face while using the UPI application?

[Probe - with installation, updation, navigation, configuration]

17) Are there any specific scenarios where you are watchful(more careful) while making transactions?

[Probe - paying to unknown/online merchant, paying using links sent via message or email]

- What do you do to protect yourself? OR what do you do about it?
- If they use more than one application, what unique challenges do they face with that application?

18) Are there any scenarios that you are concerned about while doing transactions but haven't done anything about it?

[Probe - making transactions in a hurry, verifying the authentication of the receiver etc.]

19) How do you handle any issues you come across while using UPI?

(Example scenarios - a) money got debited from your account but doesn't credit to the receiver's account, b) sent money to the wrong person etc.)

- If so can you talk about specific issue?
- Are there any other scenarios you are concerned about?

[Probe - Resolve using online information, ask friends/colleagues, contact customer support, approach law enforcement etc.]

20) Did you receive any information or guidance from the UPI provider or bank while facing challenges?

21) Are there any particular technical challenges you experienced while making the transactions?

[Probe - Internet issues, receiver device issues, QR code scanner issues etc.]

Section 5 - Safety Practices and Awareness

22) Can you give us the general safety steps you follow while using UPI?

[Probe - Strong Pin, changing pin/password frequently, not sharing pin, updating UPI app with a new version, not clicking on any links, not proceeding with transactions unless validated]

- From where did you learn these safety measures?
- Which other measures do you wish you knew?

23) Do you know any UPI settings to safeguard your transactions? If so, please name a few.

[Probe - 2-factor authentication, biometric-enabled, screen-lock enabled]

- From where did you learn these settings and configurations?
- Which other settings or features do you wish you knew?

24) Have you ever lost your phone while having UPI applications installed in it?

- If Yes, then what concerns did you have? And what measures did you take?
- If No, do you know what steps to take if you lose?

25) Have you ever given your phone to repair or exchange while having UPI applications installed in it?

- If Yes, then what concerns did you have? And what measures did you take?
- If No, do you know what steps to take if you give the phone to repair?

26) In your opinion, what measures would have helped you to develop awareness about UPI safety?

27) Is there anything else about UPI that we should have asked about or that you want to tell us?

6) Thanking at the end

"Thank you so much for taking part in the study today, I will be turning off the recording now."